

OPTIMIZATION OF METHODS OF DIAGNOSTICS OF VARIOUS FORMS OF ENDOMETRIOSIS IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE

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Abstract:

The data of informativeness of diagnostic methods of various forms of adenomyosis in women of reproductive age were carried out. It was concluded that the most informative methods are ultrasound diagnostics and hysteroscopy.

Keywords: *endometriosis, adenomyosis, forms of adenomyosis.*

Introduction

The relevance of the problem: Endometriosis is one of the pressing problems of modern gynecology due to the growing incidence, increased frequency of detection in young patients under 30 years of age and the lack of effective methods of conservative therapy. According to the Endometriosis Association of the United Kingdom, it takes an average of 5 years from the onset of the first symptoms to diagnose endometriosis. When choosing the tactics of management and treatment, it is necessary to take into account not only the form of the disease, but also the age of the patient, the severity of clinical manifestations, reproductive settings, as well as the risks and possible complications of treatment. Various authors have proposed many classifications of endometriosis.

For many years, our country has used a clinical classification of internal endometriosis of the uterine body. In this case, three forms of adenomyosis are described: diffuse (DAM), focal and nodular (UAM).

In most cases, the diagnosis is established on the basis of a histological conclusion after removal of part of the uterus or hysterectomy. At the same time, identifying the prevalence of the disease in the population is a difficult task, because The detection rate of adenomyosis in the preoperative period ranges from 2.6% to 26.0%, although the sensitivity of ultrasound and MRI is quite high and

amounts to 88%-100%. Currently, echography is mainly used to diagnose adenomyosis. According to studies [6,9], the information content of ultrasound in detecting the nodular form of adenomyosis is 93.3%. At the same time, the authors point out that it is possible to accurately diagnose the degree and form of adenomyosis in a significantly smaller number of observations. Magnetic resonance imaging has recently taken a special place in the diagnosis of adenomyosis due to its non-invasiveness and high information content. Nevertheless, advances in the field of preoperative diagnostics are not effective enough, which makes further study of these research methods relevant. In addition, there is not much data on the nodular form of adenomyosis in modern literature, which many authors even consider a special separate disease that has nothing in common with diffuse adenomyosis.

Surgical treatment remains the only radical and effective method of combating adenomyosis. Only hysterectomy can cure adenomyosis, but, according to many authors [9,10], when deciding on the extent of surgical intervention, it is necessary to take into account the age and reproductive attitude of the patient. In women of childbearing age, organ-preserving operations should be performed whenever possible.

In case of intraoperative detection of internal endometriosis, the uterus can be removed in patients who do not want to have children. An alternative method is hormonal treatment. However, in modern literature there are data on the development and successful use of organ-preserving surgical methods for the treatment of diffuse forms of adenomyosis. In patients with nodular adenomyosis who are interested in pregnancy and categorically refuse to remove the uterus, The affected areas of the uterine wall are excised with subsequent reconstruction.

However, the algorithm for choosing the volume of surgical treatment of internal endometriosis, as well as the surgical approach, has not been finally determined. The issue of the effectiveness of hormonal treatment as a method for preventing relapses of the disease after removal of the adenomyosis node also remains unstudied.

Objective of the study: To optimize the methods of diagnosis and hormonal treatment of various forms of adenomyosis in women of reproductive age.

Study materials: Forty women who received inpatient treatment for adenomyosis in the maternity hospital of Bukhara were examined. Of the 40 patients, 23 women (57.5%) had nodular adenomyosis. The remaining 17 women had diffuse adenomyosis (42.5%).

Research methods:

1. Clinical studies;
2. Ultrasound of the genital organs;
3. Hysteroscopy

Results: Anamnestic data was analyzed in 40 women with adenomyosis: 35 (87.5%) women suffered from adenomyosis pain syndrome, 24 (60%) women with nodular adenomyosis, and 11 (27.5%) women with diffuse adenomyosis.

During examination of women, the main complaints were menstrual bleeding (algodysmenorrhea, menorrhagia) in 30 (75%) women. 17 (42.5%) women with nodular adenomyosis and 10 (25%) women with diffuse adenomyosis.

Ultrasound diagnostics was the most effective examination method. Echoscopic nodular adenomyosis is characterized by not only the cellular structure of the myometrium, but also the presence of a nodular heterogeneous structure around which, unlike fibroids, there is no capsule. In the diffuse form of adenomyosis is characterized by a cellular structure of the myometrium. In

which point or small cystic structures were found, the border of the mucous membrane and the muscular layer of the uterus is not smooth, but tortuous. The thickness of the posterior wall is greater than the anterior.

Hysteroscopy is a sufficiently informative diagnostic method in 70-80% of patients, and is an addition to the ultrasound examination method.

The results of a comprehensive examination (hysteroscopy, ultrasound scanning) in 60 patients with adenomyosis (average age 35 ± 2.71 years).

Conclusions: The informativeness of ultrasound examination and detection of adenomyosis was $67.7 \pm 6.27\%$, hysteroscopy $85.5 \pm 4.17\%$.

Literature

1. Saloxiddinova, X. Y. (2024). Modern Views on the Effects of the Use of Cholecalciferol on the General Condition of the Bod. *JOURNAL OF HEALTHCARE AND LIFE-SCIENCE RESEARCH*, 3(5), 79-85.
2. Халимова, Ю. С. & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). МОРФО-ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ И КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ СТРОЕНИЯ И РАЗВИТИЯ ЯИЧНИКОВ (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ). *TADQIQOTLAR. UZ*, 40(5), 188-198.
3. Халимова, Ю. С. (2024). Морфологические Особенности Поражения Печени У Пациентов С Синдромом Мэллори-Вейса. *Journal of Science in Medicine and Life*, 2(6), 166-172.
4. Халимова, Ю. С. & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). кафедра Клинических наук Азиатский международный университет Бухара, Узбекистан. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 60-75.
5. Халимова, Ю. С. & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). МОРФО-ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ И КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ КОЖНЫХ ПОКРОВОВ. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 76-90.
6. Халимова, Ю. С. & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ЛИЦ ЗЛОУПОТРЕБЛЯЮЩЕЕСЯ ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИМИ НАПИТКАМИ. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 3-15.
7. Nematilloeva, X. M., & Salohiddinova, X. Y. (2024). LOTIN TILI VA TIBBIYOT TERMINOLOGIYASINI O'QITISHDA TALABALARDA MOTIVATSIYANI KUCHAYTIRISH YO'LLARI. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 38-48.
8. Nematilloeva, X. M., & Salohiddinova, X. Y. (2024). LOTIN TILI SIFATLARI VA DARAJALARI YASALISHINING MUHIM XUSUSIYATLARI. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 16-26.
9. Nematilloeva, X. M., & Salohiddinova, X. Y. (2024). FARMATSEVTIKADA DORI PREPARATLARI NOMLARIDA MA'NOLI BO'LAKLARNING QO'LLANILISHI. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 49-59.
10. Xalimova, Y. S. (2024). Morphology of the Testes in the Detection of Infertility. *Journal of Science in Medicine and Life*, 2(6), 83-88.
11. Хафизова, М. Н. & Халимова, Ю. С. (2024). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ЧАСТОТНЫХ ОТРЕЗКОВ В НАИМЕНОВАНИЯХ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННЫХ ПРЕПАРАТОВ В ФАРМАЦЕВТИКЕ. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 310-321.

12. Хафизова, М. Н. & Халимова, Ю. С. (2024). МОТИВАЦИОННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ ЛАТЫНИ И МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 299-309.
13. Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). ОСОБЕННОСТИ СОЗРЕВАНИЕ И ФУНКЦИОНИРОВАНИЕ ЯИЧНИКОВ. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 337-347.
14. Saloxiddinova, X. Y., & Ne'matillaeva, X. M. (2024). FEATURES OF THE STRUCTURE OF THE REPRODUCTIVE ORGANS OF THE FEMALE BODY. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 322-336.
15. Nematilloeva, X. M., & Salohiddinova, X. Y. (2024). LOTIN PREFIKSLARI ANATOMIK TERMINLAR YASALISHIDA ASOSIY KOMPONENT SIFATIDA. *Modern education and development*, 10(1), 27-37.
16. Sh, O. F., Ikhtiyarova, G. A., Xudoyqulova, F. S., & Abdieva, N. U. (2023). EFFECTIVE AND EXPRESS METHOD FOR DIAGNOSING THE CERVICAL AND VAGINA DISEASES IN REPRODUCTIVE AGE WOMEN.
17. Abdieva, N. (2024). CONDITION OF BREAST TISSUE AND THE RISK OF DEVELOPING BREAST CANCER IN PATHOLOGICAL SECERATION SYNDROME. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(4), 161-170
18. Abdieva, N. (2024). THE ROLE OF GENETIC PREDICTORS OF METABOLIC DISORDERS IN WOMEN WITH POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME CONCOMITANT WITH CERVICAL NEOPLASIA. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(3), 50-54.
19. Abdiyeva Nigina Ulugbekovna. (2024). ENDOSCOPIC-MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF BACKGROUND DISEASES OF THE CERVIX. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(4), 120–129.
20. Abdiyeva Nigina Ulugbekovna. (2024). ENDOSCOPIC-MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF BACKGROUND DISEASES OF THE CERVIX. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(4), 120–129. Retrieved from <http://web-journal.ru/index.php/journal/article/view/3052>.
21. Эргашева, Г. Т. (2023). Исследование Причин Связи Диабета 2 Типа И Ожирения. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(12), 305-311.
22. Ergasheva Gulshan Toxirovna. (2023). QANDLI DIABET 2-TUR VA SEMIZLIKNING O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIK SABABLARINI O'RGANISH. *Ta'lim Innovatsiyasi Va Integratsiyasi*, 10(3), 168–173.
23. Ergasheva Gulshan Tokhirovna. (2023). Study of clinical characteristics of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus in middle and old age. *Journal of Science in Medicine and Life*, 1(4), 16–19.
24. Saidova, L. B., & Ergashev, G. T. (2022). Improvement of rehabilitation and rehabilitation criteria for patients with type 2 diabetes.
25. Ergasheva, G. (2023). METHODS TO PREVENT SIDE EFFECTS OF DIABETES MELLITUS IN SICK PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(10), 104-108.
26. Ergasheva, G. T. (2022). QANDLI DIABET BILAN KASALLANGANLARDA REABILITATSIYA MEZONLARINI TAKOMILASHTIRISH. *TALIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(12), 335-337.

27. ГТ, Э. & Саидова, Л. Б. (2022). СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ РЕАБИЛИТАЦИОННО-ВОССТАНОВИТЕЛЬНЫХ КРИТЕРИЕВ БОЛЬНЫХ С СД-2 ТИПА. *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI*, 2(12), 206-209.
28. Toxirovna, E. G. (2023). O'RTA VA KEKSA YOSHLI BEMORLARDA 2-TUR QANDLI DIABET KECISHINING KLINIKO-MORFOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 33(1), 164-166.
29. Эргашева, Г. Т. (2023). Изучение Клинических Особенности Больных Сахарным Диабетом 2 Типа Среднего И Пожилого Возраста. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 4(6), 274-276.
30. Бакиева, М. Ш. Рустамова, Ш. Р. Рахмонов, Т. О. Шарипова, Н. Н. & Мухитдинова, Х. С. (2022). Гипотензивное действие алкалоида бензоилгетератизина на функциональную активность гладкомышечных клеток аорты крысы. *Academic Research Journal Impact Factor*, 7.
31. Samixovna, M. K. (2024). MORPHOLOGICAL DATA OF THE ORGANS OF HEMATOPOIESIS AND HEMATOPOIESIS. Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования, 14(5), 66-74.
32. Samixovna, M. K. (2024). Morphologic Changes in Red Blood Cells. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 3(3), 178-186.
33. Samixovna, M. K. (2024). MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF POSTPARTUM CHANGES IN UTERINE MEMBRANES. *SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF APPLIED AND MEDICAL SCIENCES*, 3(4), 277-283.
34. Samixovna, M. K. (2024). Current Data on Morphological and Functional Characteristics of the Thyroid Gland in Age Groups. *Journal of Science in Medicine and Life*, 2(5), 77-83.
35. Dilmurodovna, T. D. (2024). FACTORS CAUSING ESSENTIAL HYPERTENSION AND COURSE OF THE DISEASE. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(4), 138-145.
36. Dilmurodovna, T. D. (2024). PREVALENCE INDICATORS OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION IN THE POPULATION. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 41(4), 78-87.
37. Тогайдуллаева, Д. Д. (2024). ИШЕМИЧЕСКАЯ БОЛЕЗНЬ СЕРДЦА, МЕТОДЫ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ И ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ СТЕНОКАРДИИ. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 39(5), 107-115.
38. Dildora, T. (2021, June). CHRONIC RENAL FAILURE. In *Archive of Conferences* (pp. 85-89).
39. Tog'aydullayeva, D. D. (2024). MORPHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF ANEMIA IN SOMATIC DISEASES. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(4), 212-219.
40. Nematilloevna, X. M., & Qilichovna, A. M. (2024). MORPHO-FUNCTIONAL CHANGES IN ACUTE FORMS OF APHTHOUS STOMATITIS: Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari. *Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari*, 6(4), 177-186.
41. Qilichovna, A. M., & Nematilloevna, X. M. (2024). METABOLIK SINDROMI VA QON BOSIMI BOR BEMORLARDA O'ZGARISH XUSUSIYATLARI BAHOLASH: Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari. *Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari*, 6(4), 187-196.

42. Qilichovna, A. M., & Nematilloeyevna, X. M. (2024). TIBBIYOT TILI HISOBLANMISH LOTIN TILINI SAMARALI O'RGANISH OMILLARI: Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari. *Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari*, 6(4), 197-206.
43. Abdusalimovna, K. M. (2024). Current Representations of Simple Prosthodontics. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 3(3), 228-234.
44. Abdusalimovna, K. M. (2024). THE USE OF CERAMIC MATERIALS IN ORTHOPEDIC DENTISTRY. (Literature review). *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(3), 75-85.
45. Abdusalimovna, K. M. (2024). THE ADVANTAGE OF USING ALL-CERAMIC STRUCTURES. *TA'LIM VA INNOVATSION TADQIQOTLAR*, 13, 49-53.
46. Abdusalimovna, K. M. (2024). CLINICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE USE OF METAL-FREE CERAMIC STRUCTURES. *TA'LIM VA INNOVATSION TADQIQOTLAR*, 13, 45-48.
47. Кузиева, М. А. (2023). Клиникоморфологические Критерии Органов Ротовой Полости При Применении Несъемных Ортопедических Конструкций. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(12), 318-324.
48. Abdusalimovna, K. M. (2024). MORPHO-FUNCTIONAL FEATURES OF THE METHOD OF PREPARATION OF DEPULPATED TEETH FOR PROSTHETICS. *SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF APPLIED AND MEDICAL SCIENCES*, 3(4), 301-307.
49. Abdusalimovna, K. M. (2024). Clinical and Morphological Features of the Use of Non-Removable Orthopedic Structures. *JOURNAL OF HEALTHCARE AND LIFE-SCIENCE RESEARCH*, 3(5), 73-78.